

EBFMC25-OOP-12 · Investigation of the Effect of Bupivacaine and Dexmedetomidine on Wound Healing in Rat

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In this study, it was planned to investigate the effects of bupivacaine, which is widely used by local infiltration due to its analgesic properties, and dexmedetomidine, which has recently started to be used, on wound healing. It was aimed to reveal alternative possibilities for wound healing treatment by examining the early wound healing effects of bupivacaine, dexmedetomidine and their combined use in rats where wounds were created by incision.

Materials and Methods: 28 Wistar albino male rats, 6 to 8 weeks old and weighing 250-350 g, were included in the study. Rats were divided into four groups in total, 7 in each group. After the solutions determined for each group were infiltrated into the incision area, a surgical incision was made 2 minutes later and the tissues were then sutured mutually. All rats were sacrificed at the end of the 8th day and 6*4 cm skin and subcutaneous tissue were removed from the incision area in the form of a strip. Histological examination was performed with a 2 cm part of the material, hydroxyproline in the tissue with a 1 cm part, and the tensiometry device was used to calculate the tensile strength of the wound site with the remaining material (1x1 cm²). Histological evaluations were performed in the Tokat Gaziosmanpasa University Histology and Embryology Laboratory. All obtained results were evaluated statistically.

Results: In our study, consistent with the literature, it was found that IL-10 gene expression, which is considered an anti-inflammatory cytokine, was significantly higher in the group given dexmedetomidine than in the group given bupivacaine. In our study, a significant difference was found between all groups except the control and dexmedetomidine groups in terms of vascularity. It was observed that bupivacaine negatively affects wound healing and reduces the number of vessels, while dexmedetomidine increases the number of vessels, which has a positive effect, and the group using bupivacaine + dexmedetomidine formed more vessels than bupivacaine but less than dexmedetomidine.

Conclusion: In light of the data we obtained in our study, we think that bupivacaine has a negative effect on wound healing, while dexmedetomidine has a positive effect on wound healing in general. We believe that when these two drugs are used together, dexmedetomidine slightly reduces the negative effects of bupivacaine. More studies are needed to fully reveal this effect.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Bupivacaine, dexmedetomidine, wound healing, inflammation, wound infiltration

INTRODUCTION

Tissue losses that occur due to the disruption of the integrity of body structures are called ‘wounds’. Wound healing occurs as a result of the integration of a series of cellular, biochemical and physiological events. Wound healing consists of a series of complex, dynamic but well-organized events. Wound healing is an important situation in terms of patient comfort, infection risk and mortality, which we encounter in many places together with surgical incision. Many studies continue to be conducted for wound healing. Various

animal models have been tried in the literature to understand the pathophysiology of wound healing. Although none of the existing animal models can fully mimic the pathology in humans, these models are necessary to understand the pathophysiology of wound healing and to develop new treatment strategies (Irwin et al., 2002). Bupivacaine is one of the amide derivative local anesthetics. This drug has been shown to have both anesthesia and analgesia effects in local infiltration. The effects of bupivacaine, which is frequently used to reduce pain on the wound site, on wound healing have been shown to be controversial by various studies. In clinical anesthesia management, the sympatholytic, anxiolytic, analgesic and sedative effects of dexmedetomidine, a selective alpha 2 adrenergic receptor agonist, are utilized. Many experimental and clinical studies have shown that dexmedetomidine administration has anti inflammatory effects. In this study, we planned to investigate the effects of bupivacaine, which is widely used with local infiltration, and dexmedetomidine, which has recently been used, on wound healing when used together.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted in the TOGÜ Experimental Animals Laboratory, Biotechnology Department Cell Culture Laboratory, Histology and Embryology Laboratory after receiving approval from the Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University (TOGÜ) Animal Experiments Local Ethics Committee with the decision numbered 51879863-70. 28 Wistar albino male rats weighing 250-350 g, aged 6-8 weeks, were included in the study. The rats were kept at room temperature (22-24oC), with an average relative humidity of 35%, in a 12-hour light-12-hour dark environment until the beginning of the study and monitored by feeding with standard pellet feed and water. No feed and water restrictions were applied. Rats were divided into four groups, 7 in each group, as control group, bupivacaine group, dexmedetomidine group, bupivacaine and dexmedetomidine group. All rats in the groups were anesthetized with 50 mg/kg ketamine intraperitoneally. When necessary, maintenance ketamine (half dose, 25 mg/kg) was repeated by looking at reflex responses (jaw or skeletal muscle tone monitoring) to keep the depth of anesthesia constant. Rats were fixed to the operation table in prone position after anesthesia. Back hair was shaved clean with an electric shaver. The incision area was wiped with povidone iodine and dried with sterile gauze after waiting for 2 minutes (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Shaving the back area after anesthesia and painting the skin with povidone iodine

After the solutions determined for each group were infiltrated into the incision area, 2 minutes later, a perforated compress was placed under sterile conditions and a 4 cm longitudinal surgical incision was made with a scalpel along the midline from the back region, and then the skin and subcutaneous tissues were reciprocally connected with a 3/0 prolene thread (Figure 2).

Figure 2

Appearance after the subcutaneous tissues are joined together after the incision

After the procedure, 30 mg/kg, 1-2 ml acetaminophen was given as a painkiller through drinking water. No antibiotics were given at any stage of the procedure or after the procedure. The rats were kept in the same environment under optimum living conditions, with the same food and water needs met, for 8 days in shelters. Wound care was performed once a day. The animals were sacrificed under anesthesia with intraperitoneal ketamine on the 8th day after the procedure. All rats were sacrificed at the end of the 8th day and 6x4 cm skin and subcutaneous tissue were removed as a strip from the incision area on the back under sterile conditions. Histological examination was performed with a 2 cm section of the material, hydroxyproline in the tissue was performed with a 1 cm section, and the tensiometry device was used to calculate the tensile strength of the wound site with the remaining material (1x1 cm²). Tnf-alpha, interleukin 6 and interleukin 10 levels were studied with the RT-PCR method with intracardiac blood taken at 0 hours. In addition, the ELISA method was used to analyze the hydroxyproline level in the tissues. The hydroxyproline ELISA test was performed with the protocol specified by the company in the Rat Hyp (Hydroxyproline) ELISA Kits of A.B.T Laboratory Industry.

Single-stranded cDNA was made from total RNA isolated from each sample with iScript Reverse Transcriptase Supermix. Real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction was performed on qTOWER3G Real-Time PCR Thermocycler.

Histopathological Evaluation: In order to examine the general morphological structure of the tissues, to evaluate acute inflammation, chronic inflammation and edema seen in the tissue with histochemical scoring method, Hematoxylin Eosin staining method was used technically. Then, preparations were examined with Nikon microscope (Nikon Eclipse 200) to evaluate acute inflammation, chronic inflammation and edema. In order to determine the difference in the degree of vascularization between the groups in the tissues, to count the vascular structures present in the scar area, to count the fibroblast cells present in the scar area in each group, to determine the area of the fibrous scar area formed in the tissues and to measure the epithelial thickness in the scar area and its periphery, Modified Masson Trichrome staining method was used technically. Subsequently, preparations were examined with a Nikon microscope (Nikon Eclipse 200) to evaluate vascularization, collagenization, epithelialization and fibrotic scar tissue. The Nikon NIS-Elements software was also used to make measurements.

Statistical Evaluation: While evaluating the data obtained in the study, the "Statistical Package for Social Sciences for Windows 26.0" (SPSS) program was used for statistical analysis. While evaluating the study data, the Shapiro-Wilk test was used for compliance with normal distribution. It was determined that the data were not suitable for normal distribution. Mann Whitney U Test and Kruskal Wallis Test were used to compare the groups. In cases where there was a difference, Bofferroni correction was applied to find the source of the difference and $p < 0.01$ was considered statistically significant in pairwise comparisons. The findings were evaluated at a 95% confidence interval. For all analyses except pairwise comparisons, the significance level was $p < 0.05$, which was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

When the IL-6 gene expression values were compared in pairs, a significant difference was found between the Dexmedetomidine group and the Bupivacaine group ($p=0.01$). When the IL-10 gene expression values were compared in pairs, a significant difference was found between all groups ($p=0.01$). In the comparison between the groups, a statistically significant difference was found between the groups in terms of tensiometry results ($p=0.0001$). In the comparison between the groups, a statistically significant difference was found between the groups in terms of hydroxyproline concentration ($p=0.0001$). In the comparison between the groups, a statistically significant difference was found between the groups in terms of fibrous scar area ($p=0.0001$) (Table 1, Figure 3).

Table 1

Comparison of fibrous scar area in paired groups

p value	C	B	D	B+D
C		0,002*	0,565	0,004*
B	0,002*		0,002*	0,004*
D	0,565	0,002*		0,003*
B+D	0,004*	0,004*	0,003*	

C: Control B: Bupivacaine D: Dexmedetomidine B+D: Bupivacaine+Dexmedetomidine:
Mann-Whitney U analysis and pairwise comparison of groups,
Bonferroni Correction, $p < 0.01$
*Statistical significance

Figure 3

Evaluation of fibrous scar tissue area between groups

A: Control B: Bupivacaine C: Dexmedetomidine D: Bupivacaine+Dexmedetomidine, Bar: 50 μ m

In the comparison between the groups, a statistically significant difference was found between the groups in terms of vascularity. In the histopathological examination, when vascularity was compared in paired groups, a significant difference was found between the dexmedetomidine group and the bupivacaine group, and the dexmedetomidine group and the bupivacaine+dexmedetomidine groups ($p < 0.01$) (Table 2).

Table 2

Comparison of vascularity in binary groups

p value	C	B	D	B+D
C		0,025	0,141	0,124
B	0,025		0,004*	0,200
D	0,141	0,004*		0,010
B+D	0,124	0,200	0,010	

C: Control B: Bupivacaine D: Dexmedetomidine B+D: Bupivacaine+Dexmedetomidine:
Mann-Whitney U analysis and pairwise comparison of groups,
Bonferroni Correction, $p < 0.01$
*Statistical significance

DISCUSSION

Impaired wound healing causes various negative outcomes such as increased risk of infection, increased hospital stay and cost, and decreased patient comfort (Fujita et al., 2012). Many studies are being conducted to understand the wound healing process. Although they cannot mimic human physiology, animal models are used to reveal the pathophysiology. The most commonly used models in these studies are created with rats (Dorsett-Martin, 2004). In our study, we preferred to use the low-cost rat wound model, which is closest to human physiology. There are many clinical and experimental studies showing that bupivacaine increases pro-inflammatory factor levels in the first days of wound healing and decreases anti-inflammatory factor levels, leading to pro-inflammatory effects, causing high edema and inflammation, and also reducing collagen production. In a study conducted by Özgergin et al., it was shown that bupivacaine, ropivacaine and levobupivacaine reduced the expression levels of TNF α , IL-1 and IL-6 (Oz Gergin et al., 2019). There are many experimental and clinical studies showing that dexmedetomidine has anti-inflammatory effects by reducing the levels of pro-inflammatory factors and increasing the levels of anti-inflammatory factors. In a meta-analysis study, postoperative TNF- α , IL-6, IL-8 and IL-10 levels were examined in patients who received perioperative dexmedetomidine in various surgeries. According to the obtained data, TNF- α and IL-6 levels were significantly reduced (Li et al., 2015). A meta-analysis study including 15 randomized controlled trials examining the effects of dexmedetomidine showed that the addition of dexmedetomidine to general anesthesia in the perioperative period decreased the postoperative TNF- α , IL-6 and IL-8 serum levels of the patients compared to the control group, while IL-10 levels increased compared to the control group (Li et al., 2015). In our study, IL-10 gene expression was found to be significantly different in all groups compared to the control group. IL-10 gene expression decreased in the bupivacaine group and increased in the dexmedetomidine group. An increase similar to the dexmedetomidine group was observed in the bupivacaine + dexmedetomidine group. These data in our study support the literature on bupivacaine and dexmedetomidine. Furthermore, our results show that dexmedetomidine corrects the negative effects of bupivacaine on IL-10. While IL-6 gene expression was not different from the control group in any group, TNF- α gene expression was similar between the groups. In 2 different studies where TNF- α and IL-6 levels were measured by intraoperative dexmedetomidine infusion, it was observed that TNF- α and IL-6 levels did not change, similar to our study (Lee et al., 2022). In the study by Taniguchi et al., it was shown that dexmedetomidine changes TNF- α and IL-6 levels in a dose-dependent manner (Taniguchi et al., 2008). We also believe that the fact that we could not clearly demonstrate the effects of dexmedetomidine on TNF- α and IL-6 in our study may be due to the dose. Moreover, we did not examine the expressions of these interleukins in the period immediately after the incision. We think that examining the effect on the change with repeated measurements will reveal very different results.

Acute inflammation develops suddenly and can last for a few hours or a few days, vasodilation due to inflammation is observed and as a result, exudation of fluid and plasma proteins occurs from the postcapillary venules in the area of inflammation. Edema develops after this, and leukocytes begin to migrate to the area of damage. In a study by Hancı et al., saline, lidocaine, bupivacaine and tramadol were infiltrated into the wound area. They found that edema and inflammation scores were significantly higher in the bupivacaine and lidocaine groups than in the control group (Hancı et al., 2012). In our study, cell edema was also significantly increased in the bupivacaine group compared to the other groups. Another critical factor determining the effect on wound healing is wound tensile strength. It has been determined that collagen is an important biomarker of the wound healing process that provides support and strength (Chithra, Sajithlal, & Chandrakasan, 1998). Collagen synthesis can be assessed by hydroxyproline concentration. After proline was administered to the wounds opened on the backs of rats and the wound healing was monitored on the 4th and 8th days, it was observed that the wounds healed very quickly (Ponrasu et al., 2013). In the study conducted by Hancı et al., in the samples taken on the 8th day after saline, lidocaine, bupivacaine and tramadol were infiltrated into the wound site, collagen production and fracture strength were significantly decreased in the bupivacaine and lidocaine groups compared to the control group (Hancı et al., 2012). In our study, bupivacaine decreased hydroxyproline levels similar to the literature findings. Hydroxyproline levels were found to be high in the groups where dexmedetomidine was applied alone or together with bupivacaine. There is no study in the literature examining the effects of dexmedetomidine on hydroxyproline. At the same time, wound tensile strength was significantly increased in the dexmedetomidine group, while it was the lowest in the bupivacaine group. When dexmedetomidine was administered together with bupivacaine, higher wound tensile strength and hydroxyproline levels were detected compared to the control group. We believe that dexmedetomidine

has positive effects on wound tensile strength and collagen synthesis and may even reverse the negative effects of bupivacaine when administered together. Fibroblasts are critically important in supporting normal wound healing; they are involved in fundamental processes such as fibrin clot breakdown, new extracellular matrix and the formation of collagen structures to support other cells associated with effective wound healing (Ponrasu et al., 2013). In an in vitro study in which human fibroblasts were exposed to lidocaine, bupivacaine, and ropivacaine for 2 days, a concentration-dependent decrease in mitochondrial activity and proliferation rate of living cells was observed. Among the local anesthetics analyzed, bupivacaine showed the most severe cytotoxic effect (Fedder et al., 2010). In our study, bupivacaine decreased fibroblast numbers similar to the literature, while dexmedetomidine increased them. When used together, positive effects on fibroblast numbers were detected. While the fibrous scar area was similar in the control and dexmedetomidine groups, it was higher in the groups where bupivacaine was used alone or together with dexmedetomidine. When the number of fibroblasts per unit area of fibrous scar was examined, it was seen that the dexmedetomidine group was even better than the control group, while the bupivacaine + dexmedetomidine group was similar to the control and better than the bupivacaine group. In the bupivacaine + dexmedetomidine group, the fibrotic scar area was large, but dense regenerated epithelium and connective tissue were observed within this area. The fact that the fiber bundles in the areas where collagen fibers are dominant are denser and thicker than those in the periphery indicates that these areas are healing. This shows us that dexmedetomidine reduces the scar tissue-forming effect of bupivacaine.

Vascularity is a critical component of wound healing (Martin, Semple, & Sefton, 2010). In the wound site study conducted by Hancı et al., the vascularity values of the groups to which bupivacaine was applied on the 8th day were significantly reduced compared to the control group. In our study, we also found that the number of vessels in the bupivacaine group was less than the dexmedetomidine group. When the vascularity rate in the fibrous scar area was examined, it was seen that bupivacaine significantly reduced vascularity compared to all other groups. However, dexmedetomidine did not have a significant positive effect on vascularity compared to the control group. There are some restrictive factors in our study. We conducted our experiment with a small number of subjects in a rat model due to ethical reasons. We only investigated the data on a single day regarding early wound healing. We believe that our study will shed light on future clinical studies.

CONCLUSION

In our study, we investigated the effects of bupivacaine, dexmedetomidine and their combined use on wound healing with wound infiltration. In light of the data we obtained in our study, we think that bupivacaine alone has a negative effect on wound healing, while dexmedetomidine generally has positive effects on wound healing. We believe that when these two drugs are used together, the negative effect of bupivacaine is slightly reduced. More studies are needed to fully demonstrate this effect.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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